

Synthesis and biological significance of 2-aminobenzothiazole derivatives

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Manuscript received 12 June 2007, revised 27 September 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : Several new 2-*N*-(substituted benzylidene)-imino-1,3-benzothiazole **1**; 2-[2'-(substituted phenyl)-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazole **2** and 2-[5'-(arylidene)-2'-substituted phenyl-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazole **3** have been synthesized and evaluated for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma viride* and antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords : 2-Aminobenzothiazole, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Benzothiazole derivatives are known to possess several biological activities such as antitubercular¹, antiallergic², antimicrobial³ and fungicidal⁴⁻⁶. 1,3-Thiazolidines have been reported to display antiinflammatory^{7,8}, fungicidal⁹⁻¹¹, antibiotic¹², antitubercular¹³, antibacterial¹⁴, anti-convulsant¹⁵ and antifungal activities¹⁶. 5-Benzylidene-1,3-thiazolidine-4-ones show good pharmacological properties¹². In the present study position 2 in the 2-aminobenzothiazole moiety having -NH₂ group was used as the target for chemical modification. Hence we have introduced 2-oxo-azetidone and their 5-benzylidene moieties in 2-aminobenzothiazole framework.

Results and discussion

2-Aminobenzothiazole on reaction with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of acetic acid to give 2-*N*-(substituted benzylidene)-imino-1,3-benzothiazole **1**. The compound **1** on treatment with thioglycolic acid in the presence of ZnCl₂ yielded 2-[2'-(substituted phenyl)-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazole **2** which on further treatment with various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of potassium ethoxide afforded 2-[5'-(benzylidene)-2'-substituted phenyl-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazoles **3** (Scheme 1).

The compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma viride* by paper disc technique at two concentrations (100 and 500 ppm) and antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*

at two concentrations (50 and 100 ppm) by filter paper disc technique¹¹. Standard antifungal Griseofulvin and antibacterial streptomycin were also screened under the similar conditions for comparison.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in an open capillary tubes. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹) and ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz on Bruker DRX 300 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ , ppm). The mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

2-*N*-(Substituted benzylidene)-imino-1,3-benzothiazole (**1a**) :

Equimolar solution of 2-aminobenzothiazole (5 g, 0.03 mol) and benzaldehyde (3.38 ml, 0.03 mol) with few drops of glacial acetic acid in MeOH (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about 1 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified over the column of silica gel using CHCl₃ as an eluent. The product was crystallized from ethanol to give **1a**, 75%, m.p. 106–107 °C (Found : C, 70.55; H, 4.18; N, 11.74. C₁₄H₁₀N₂S requires : C, 70.58; H, 4.20; N, 11.76%); ν_{\max} 3041, 1572, 1525, 1180, 1076, 740 and 788 (benzothiazole with aromatic ring), 1547 (N=CH); δ 7.12–7.95 (9H, m, Ar-H), 4.92 (1H, δ , N=CH); MS : 238 (M⁺).

Other compounds **1b-k** were synthesized similarly from 2-aminobenzothiazole using different aromatic aldehydes. Characterization data are presented in Table 1.

2-[2'-(Substituted phenyl)-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazole (2a) :

A mixture of the compound **1** (3 g, 0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.91 ml, 0.01 mol) in the presence of ZnCl₂ in benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about 15 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified over the column of silica gel using CHCl₃ as an eluent. The product was crystallized from ethanol to afford compound **2a**, 72%, m.p. 151–152° (Found : C, 61.51; H, 3.82; N, 8.94. C₁₆H₁₂ON₂S₂ requires : C, 61.53; H, 3.84; N, 8.97%); ν_{\max} 3038, 1575, 1521, 1178, 1075, 1032, 738 and 785 (benzothiazole with aromatic ring), 2968 (CH₂-S cyclic), 1715 (>C=O cyclic), 1318 (C-N), 2982 (N-CH-S); δ 3.18 (1H, s, -N-CH), 4.48 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 3.22 (1H, s, N-CH-Ar), 7.23–7.51 (9H, m, Ar-H); MS : 312 (M⁺).

 Table 1. Yield and melting points of the compounds **1b-k**, **2b-k** and **3b-k**

Compd.	Ar ¹	Ar ²	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
1b	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	72	115–117
1c	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	70	108–111
1d	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	73	107–109
1e	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	71	108–110
1f	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	70	109–111
1g	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	72	112–114
1h	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	69	104–106
1i	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	68	107–109
1j	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	70	112–114
1k	4,4'-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	–	75	111–113
2b	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	69	145–147
2e	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	70	140–142
2d	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	–	71	143–144
2e	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	72	139–141
2f	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	68	137–138
2g	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	73	139–142
2h	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	70	140–141
2i	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	71	138–140
2j	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	–	73	133–134
2k	4,4'-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	–	68	135–137
3b	–	2-BrC ₆ H ₄	59	195–197
3e	–	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	60	192–194
3d	–	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	62	198–199
3e	–	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	65	200–201
3f	–	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	61	199–202
3g	–	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	63	197–198
3h	–	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	66	203–205
3i	–	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	67	201–203
3j	–	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	64	200–204
3k	–	4,4'-N(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	65	203–205

 Table 2. Antifungal activity of the compounds **1a-k**, **2a-k** and **3a-k** against various fungi at different concentrations (ppm)

Compd.	<i>A. niger</i>		<i>A. flavus</i>		<i>F. oxysporum</i>		<i>T. viride</i>	
	100	500	100	500	100	500	100	500
1a	+	++	–	–	+	++	+	+
1b	++	++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	++
1e	+++	++++	++	+++	++	++	++	+++
1d	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	++
1e	++	+++	++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++
1f	++	++	+	++	++	++	++	+++
1g	+	++	++	++	++	+++	+++	+++
1h	++	+++	–	+	+	++	++	++
1i	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	+++
1j	++	++	–	+	+	+	+	++
1k	+	++	–	–	–	+	+	++
2a	+	+	+	+	–	–	+	+
2b	++	++	+	++	++	+++	++	++
2e	+++	++++	+	++	++	+++	++	+++
2d	++	++	–	+	+++	++++	++	+++
2e	++	+	–	+	++	++	+	++
2f	++	++	+	+	+	+	++	++
2g	+	+	+	++	–	+	++	+
2h	+	+	–	+	–	–	+	–
2i	+	+	+	+	–	+	+	+
2j	+	+	–	+	–	–	+	+
2k	–	–	+	++	++	+++	+	++
3a	–	–	+	+	–	+	+	+
3b	++	++	+	++	++	+++	++	++
3c	+++	++++	+	++	++	++	++	++
3d	++	++	++	+++	+++	++++	++	+++
3e	++	+	–	+	++	++	+	++
3f	++	++	+	+	+	+	++	++
3g	+	+	+	++	–	+	++	+
3h	+	+	–	+	–	–	+	–
3i	+	+	+	+	–	+	+	+
3j	+	+	–	+	–	–	+	+
3k	–	–	+	++	+	+++	+	++
GF	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

GF Griseofulvin; inhibition diameter in mm; (–) 5; (+) 5–11; (++) 11–15; (+++) 15–19; (++++) 19–24.

Other compounds **2b-k** (Table 1) were synthesized similarly from compound **1**. All of them gave satisfactory analytical data.

2-[5'-(Benzylidene)-2'-substituted phenyl-4'-oxo-1',3'-thiazolidine]-1,3-benzothiazole (**3a**) :

Equimolar solution of compound **3** (2 g, 0.006 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.65 ml, 0.006 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) in the presence of C_2H_5OK was refluxed on a water bath for about 6 h. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was purified over the column of silica gel using $CHCl_3$ as an eluent. The product was crystallized from ethanol to yield compound **3**, 58%, m.p. 202–203° (Found : C, 71.48; H, 4.11; N, 3.60. $C_{23}H_{16}ON_2S_2$ requires : C, 71.50; N, 4.14; S, 3.62%); ν_{max} 3036, 1572, 1517, 1174, 1072, 1033, 730 and 782 (benzothiazole with aromatic ring), 1620 ($C=CHAr$), 1713 ($>C=O$ cyclic), 1320 (C-N), 2980 (N-CH-S); δ 3.15 (1H, s, -N-CH), 5.20 (1H, s, $C=CHAr$), 7.04–7.91 (14H, m, Ar-H); MS : 386 (M^+).

Scheme 1

Table 3 . Antibacterial activity of the compounds **1a-k**, **2a-k** and **3a-k** against various bacteria at different concentrations (ppm)

Compd.	<i>B. subtilis</i>		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>K. pneumoniae</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	
	50	100	50	100	50	100	50	100
1a	+	+	-	+	+	++	+	+
1b	+++	+++	++	++	+	++	++	++
1e	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++++
1d	++	++	+++	++++	++	+++	+++	+++
1e	++	++	++	++	++	+++	+	+++
1f	+	+	+	++	+	++	+	++
1g	++	++	+	++	+	+	++	++
1h	+	++	-	+	+	+	+	++
1i	+	++	-	-	-	-	+	++
1j	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	++
1k	+	++	-	+	+	+	+	+
2a	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+
2b	++	+	+	++	+	+	+	++
2c	+++	++++	++	++	+	++	+	+
2d	++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++	+++	++++
2e	++	++	++	+++	+++	+++	++	++
2f	+	++	+	++	++	++	+	++
2g	++	++	+	++	++	++	+++	+++
2h	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
2i	+	+	+	-	++	+	+	+
2j	+	++	+	-	+	+	++	+
2k	-	+	++	+	++	++	+	++
3a	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+
3b	++	+	+	++	+	+	+	++
3c	+++	++++	++	++	+	++	+	+
3d	++	+++	+++	++++	+++	+++	+++	++++
3e	++	++	++	+++	+++	+++	++	++
3f	+	++	+	++	++	++	+	++
3g	++	++	+	++	++	++	+++	+++
3h	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
3i	+	+	+	-	++	+	+	+
3j	+	++	+	-	+	+	++	+
3k	-	+	++	+	++	++	+	++
SM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

SM Streptomycin; inhibition diameter in mm; (-) 4; (+) 5–11; (+ +) 11–17, (++ +) 17–23; (+ + + +) 23–29.

Other compounds **3b-k** (Table 1) were synthesized similarly from compound **2** using different aromatic aldehydes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow for providing the spectral and analytical data of the compounds. We are also thankful to the Heads, Department

of Biotechnology for antimicrobial activity and Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing the laboratory facilities.

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